
Barriers and Enablers to Effective Maternal Health Campaigns on Social Media Platforms in Nigeria

Hussaina Abaji Abdullahi; Prof. Moses Ter Akase & Prof. Kaior Samuel Akpede

Department of Mass Communication

Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria

hussainaabdul202@gmail.com; abaji.abdullahi@socsci.fulafia.edu.ng

+2347037766220

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Abstract

This study was carried out to explore the factors that facilitate or hinder the effectiveness of maternal health campaign on social media platforms in Nigeria. The enablers include digital literacy by providing training to users on how to enhances their competence in using digital health tools, engaging community members in health campaigns had increased the confidence and satisfaction among service users, contributing to their trust in healthcare providers and healthcare systems and interactive feature of the social media platforms such as immediate feedback proves to be of advantage , while barriers examined in this study are digital divide such as poor network and misinformation on social media platforms proves to be a disadvantage to health outcomes. The researchers adopted the media richness theory, which argue that media choice influences message effectiveness. The researchers adopted the library research method. The findings revealed that despite the challenges of using social media for maternal health campaigns, these campaigns are seen to be effective by facilitating awareness on maternal health issues, promoting healthier maternal behaviour and extend reach of maternal information. This study suggested that government and private organisations should carryout orientations on digital literacy and limit digital divide in Nigeria. The paper concludes that social media platforms offer more good than harm in passing health information in Nigeria.

Keywords: Enablers, Barriers, Maternal Health, Social Media, Campaigns

Introduction

Maternal health remains a public health challenge in Nigeria, a country that accounts for a large part of global maternal mortality rate. According to World Health Organisation (2023), Nigerian maternal mortality rate is 1,047 deaths in every 10,000 live births. The lifetime challenges of a Nigerian woman dying during pregnancy, childbirth, postpartum or post abortion is 1 in 22; as against the lifetime risk in developed countries estimated at 1 in 4900 live births.” WHO (2023), reports that “in every 2 minutes, one Nigerian woman dies and for each casualty.” There are several women who will have lifelong problems and no access to medical care. Nigeria is one of the countries with the highest maternal mortality rates in the world, where many women are facing barriers in accessing health care services during pregnancy and childbirth. Recently, social media platforms have become important tools for health communication, providing different ways to share

information, engage communities and impact health behaviours (Korda & Itani, 2021).

Social media platforms have changed the way health communication is disseminated and accessed. These platforms enable communication, interaction, engagements and outreach, making it suitable for public health awareness campaigns, including maternal health awareness campaigns. Studies have shown that social media engagements help facilitate positive health seeking behaviors and improve health information knowledge among pregnant women and mothers (Lupton, 2021). Leveraging on social media platforms for maternal health campaigns will significantly improve and promote healthy maternal outcomes.

However, the effectiveness of social media maternal health campaigns is often influenced by barriers such as limited internet access especially in rural communities, low digital literacy, fake news, misinformation and social economic factors such as cultural beliefs and attitudes toward health seeking behavior, which can, consequently, affect social media message reach and impact. However, factors such as youth engagements, wide mobile phone usage and partnership with health professionals serve as enablers (Adebayo et al., 2022). Moreover, social media platforms facilitate interactive communication, allowing immediate feedback and community engagement which can aid community members to have sense of ownership and participation among social media users.

This study aims to explore the barriers and enablers of maternal health campaigns on social media in Nigeria by identifying factors that promote maternal health campaign and barriers of these campaigns on social media platforms. The research seeks to provide insights that can help the design and implementation of more effective health communication strategies which will contribute to improved maternal outcomes.

Conceptual Overview

Enablers

Enablers are factors or conditions that enhance the effectiveness of a particular process, intervention or initiative. The enablers of maternal health campaign on social media are elements that support the successful dissemination of information, engage target audience which lead to the improvement of maternal health outcomes. Enablers can be classified into social, technological and organisational. Social enablers may include community engagements, cultural relevance and the involvement of community leaders which can promote maternal health message reception. Technological enablers include social media accessibility and usability. According to Halka & Nasereddin (2025), social media enhance health awareness among pregnant women by providing effective communication channels for disseminating health related information on pregnancy and maternal care. Organisational enablers involve partnerships with health organisations, training of health communicators and integrated feedback mechanism. Osi *et al* (2021) highlight how community engagements and involvement is an enabler in health campaigns as it promotes trust and increases positive behavior change among targeted population. Similarly, Akintola *et al* (2020) posit that culturally tailored messages are impactful enablers in promoting health interventions in diverse populations.

Barriers

Barriers are obstacle that prevent or hinders the success or effectiveness of a particular campaign or initiative. Barriers to effective maternal health campaign are factors that hinder the success of disseminating, accepting and impacting on health-related messages aimed at improving maternal health. Barriers of maternal health campaign on social media can be categorise into technological barrier, socio-cultural barrier, institutional barrier and content related barrier. According to Olanrewaju *et al* (2022) technological barriers include limited internet access, especially in rural areas, high cost of data and poor digital infrastructure which limit access to social media platforms. While Okereke *et al.* (2021) observed that in many communities in Nigeria, topics on reproductive and maternal health are still considered a taboo which in turn reduce the likelihood of women to engage with social media contents on maternal health. Nigerian institutions have inadequate coordinated strategies, limited funding for digital campaigns and insufficient training of health professionals in digital communication. Without institutional support, social media campaign may lack consistency and professional oversight (Adebayo *et al* 2022). The spread of misleading health information on social media platforms and the failure to adapt content to digital behavior of the target audience are other factors to contend with. Misleading information on social media platforms can erase trust and reduce credibility of health messages, thereby diminishing the goals of maternal health campaigns (Olapegba *et al* 2021).

Maternal health

Maternal health is health care provided to women of childbearing age, before, during and after pregnancy (prenatal, antenatal and postnatal). Maternal health remains a cornerstone of global public health efforts to ensure the well-being of women and children during the fragile phase of pregnancy. The World Health Organisation (WHO, 2020) sees maternal health as the health of women during pregnancy, childbirth and the postpartum period, including the care she receives before, during and after pregnancy. While Kidist *et al* (2019) argue that maternal health is a woman's ability to adapt physiologically, psychologically and socially to the maternal role, resulting in optimal maternal and child health. Globally, maternal mortality is “horribly high,” totaling 800 preventable deaths per day, with a maternal death happening every 2 minutes (MacDorman *et al* 2016; WHO, 2023). Maternal health is an important part of public health, which is mainly caused by various factors such as social, economic, cultural, demographic and behavioral factors. More than 50% of maternal deaths occur one week or more after delivery, and 80% of pregnancy-related mortality is preventable (Creanga *et al* 2014; CDC, 2022). Competent maternal care services are critical to aid the survival of mother and child.

Social Media

Social media platforms refer to digital media platforms and applications that permit users to create, share and interact with content and connect with others worldwide. These platforms make communication and cooperation through various forms of media, including text, pictures, videos and sound. Allcott & Gentzkow (2017) see social media

as a wide range of Internet applications structured on the conceptual and technological foundations of Web 2.0 that support the creation and sharing of user-generated content. Social media has brought about a major transformation in communication worldwide with its vast reach and ability to share ideas and information quickly (Abdulsalam & Suraju 2024). Social media can be described as a computer technology that allows users to spread information and ideas through virtual networks between groups and communities via the Internet. Thomas *et al* (2020), posits that social media platforms, by their very nature, can educate, entertain audiences and subscribers, and control impact that traditional media lacks. Users typically download services or applications that gives access to social media functionality to their smartphones or tablets. They create interactive platforms where individuals, organisations and communities can discuss, participate, co-create, share, edit user-generated or self-curated content that is published online (Brian Dean, 2023). Sutrisno *et al* (2023) noted that social media have advanced, in addition to being only a tool for social interaction. Tandon *et al* (2020) noted that information shared on social media platforms such as Facebook, if not restricted, can be viewed by anyone with internet connectivity on and off the platform. Social media platforms break down geographical borders and form communities that share similar interest and goal. According to Anderson (2019), the primary reason people are actively on social media, is for security or comfort, but because they are happy with the value of the service provided by the media. Thakur & Chandar (2018) identified popular social media platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp and YouTube; they further emphasise Facebook as the most popular. Social media has evidently become a strong force in reshaping interactions, information sharing and community building, offering unprecedented opportunities for connection and engagements in the society. In 2019, social media engagement shows notable trends with platforms emphasising visual contents maintaining significant popularity among younger demographics; notably, 67% of 18 to 29 years old used Instagram and 62% used snapchat (Pew Research Center, 2019).

Enablers of Effective Maternal Health Campaign on Social Media Platforms

Digital Literacy: Providing training to users enhances their competence in using digital health tools. Digital literacy allows pregnant women and new mothers to access vital information online. Nwanko *et al* (2021) observed that women who are digitally literate are empowered to likely seek healthcare services and obey medical advice. In a study by Udenigwe *et al* (2022) the Text4life programme in Edo State established that women trained to use mobile health (mHealth) leads to utilisation of maternal health services. Similarly, the MAAMI initiative uses mobile phone technology to provide health education to pregnant women, showcasing the importance of digital literacy in accessing health information (TechWoman, 2025).

Community Engagements and Trust: Community engagement is important in promoting the acceptability and effectiveness of maternal health campaigns. A study by

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Okonofua *et al* (2022) emphasised the role of trust in sustaining the provision and uptake of maternal and child healthcare services in Nigeria. The study found incentives offered by health programmes to community members have increased the confidence and satisfaction among service users, contributing to their trust in healthcare providers and healthcare systems. Involving community members in key decision-making processes ensures that the campaigns are culturally appropriate and tailored to community members. Ntoimo *et al* (2021) states that community participatory approach increased community improved maternal health outcomes.

A study by Britto *et al* (2018) discussed how the use social media for spreading key reports becomes common, especially in campaigns related to the importance of health. Using Twitter (X), Instagram and Facebook, it is attention in online public life with hashtag campaigns. The study focused on assessing the characteristics of health campaigns related to hashtag on social media platforms and comparing three different campaigns across three commonly used social media platforms.

Another study by Muhtar *et al* (2024) explored the increase in the use of social networks and how health communication has been revolutionised by providing an important platform with a global attraction for the dissemination of information and defense of public health. The study explains how effective social networks can be to improve public health defense and increase public health awareness. Using a mixed method approach, which combines the analysis of qualitative and quantitative content, the results reveal that visually attractive materials, such as infographics and brief videos, are more effective to get attention and improve user participation for health defense purposes.

Similarly, a study by Ogundani *et al* (2024) provides an extensive review of the use of digital health technology (DHT) to improve maternal health care in sub-Saharan Africa. The study focused on the capacity of digital interventions to improve access and use of maternal health services in underserved areas and the effectiveness of these efforts in the perinatal and postpartum periods and assessment of problems. They used reviewed publications from 2020 to 2023 by searching online databases using specific keywords and selecting literature that mainly discussed digital health interventions in maternal health. Findings showed that while utilisation of maternal health services is low, the use of digital technologies such as mobile health (mHealth) applications to reach underserved populations is increasing. These studies show that social media platforms despite some challenges are reliable enablers for maternal health campaign.

Barriers of Effective Maternal Health Campaigns on Social Media Platforms

Misinformation: Misinformation on social media platform can reduce the effect of maternal health campaign on social media platforms. According to John *et al* (2024), misinformation about reproductive health is a disadvantage to health outcomes which in turn compromises medical trust and allows misinformed policy restrictions. Health information that is misleading or fake is seen as a threat to health outcome because the interaction between patients and health personnel are built on trust. While access to maternal health on social media can empower women, it also exposes them to misinformation, conflicting advice and too much contents consumption which can result

to confusion and decisions based on content consume from unreliable sources (Chaney & Mechael, 2024). Misleading information on social media can reduce trust and credibility of health messages which defeats the goal of maternal health campaigns (Olapegba *et al* 2021). The spread of misinformation can affect women and stop them from seeking proper healthcare services.

Digital Divide: with the wide spread of social media utilisation in Nigeria, there is a divide between rural communities and the urban communities. Van-Diajk (2020) noted that digital divide includes inequality in access to digital technologies, digital literacy and the ability to effectively use digital tools. Social media campaign relies on internet connectivity. According to Nigerian Communications Commission (2022), internet growth is increasing but most rural areas remain offline. The inadequate access to social support through social media can affect women in rural areas who might feel isolated.

Review of Empirical Studies

Several studies have been carried out in relations to social media use for maternal health campaign. Olusegun (2024) in his study titled: Impact of Digital Platform on Nigerian Women's Attitude toward Contraceptives. The findings showed that online health campaign have increased awareness and positive attitude towards contraceptives and suggest the need to strategise online health to improve the effectiveness of online health interventions. The similarity between the reviewed study and the current study is that they both dwell on digital media health campaign; the difference, however, is that the reviewed work focuses on the impact of digital media and women's attitude towards contraceptives, while the current study lays emphasis on the barriers and enablers to effective maternal health campaigns on social media. In another study by Omosola *et al* (2025) titled: Exploring Doctors and Midwives Perspective on Utilising Social Media for Maternal Health Promotion. The findings from the study underscored the potentials of social media as tools for doctors and midwives to promote maternal health, with platforms like Facebook, WhatsApp and Instagram empowering healthcare providers to enhance patient education, foster engagement and offer support to expecting mothers.

Similarly, another study by Sharma *et al* (2024) titled Association between Media Exposure and Maternal Health Service Use in Nepal Demographic and Health Survey-2022. The findings showed that women exposed to the media and internet 84.5% complete their antenatal care than women not exposed to the media. The similarity between this study and the current study is that they both dwell on maternal health promotion with the reviewed study focusing on media exposure and the current study focusing on enablers and barriers to maternal health campaigns on social media platforms. Another study by Momanyi (2023) titled: Digital Media and Maternal Healthcare among Young Women in Kenya. The findings of the study showed that 88% of the participants preferred internet search for information while 92% uses different digital media platforms during pregnancy. The similarity between the current study and the reviewed study is that both focus on maternal health awareness; the difference, however, is that the reviewed study focused on Kenya while the current study focuses on Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

Media Richness Theory

Introduced in 1984 by Richard L. Daft & Robert H. Lengal, the theory describes and evaluates communication media within an organisation in terms of their effectiveness. The goal of the theory is to provide managers with a means to describe and explain the communication challenges that organisations face. According to the theory, different media or forms of communication have different levels of information richness that they provide. The theory is based on a model of information processing by organisations (Galbraith, 1977; Tushman & Nadler, 1978). Smith & Aparico (2023) stated that "advances in social media, virtual teams, globalisation and telecommunication networks present an alternative to face-to-face meetings, noting that media richness theory assumes that task performance is tailored to a medium that can convey information." Miles (2012) observed that communication media have different levels of power and show their different potentials in information capacity. Daft & Lengal considered media richness theory as a perspective model, with their original research suggesting that high and low levels of media richness have their own distinct advantages in terms of reducing either equivocality or uncertainty.

Criticism of media richness theory is that it assumes a fixed hierarchy of media richness, placing face-to-face communication at the top and written or text communication at the bottom (Daft & Lengal, 1986). However, this ranking does not account for how individuals adapt to different media overtime; similarly, the theory overlook that media consumers have different preferences, familiarity and social context in selecting what media to consume with critics arguing that media choice is not based on task only, but also on social norms, convenience and personal habits (Carlson & Zmud, 1999). Despite its criticisms, media richness is relevant to this paper because it helps the understanding of how communication medium influences message effectiveness on social media platforms as tools of maternal health campaign through its multiple functions of adapting different features like video, audio, text and images.

Methodology

The study adopted library research method aimed at explaining the enablers and barriers to effective maternal health campaigns on social media platforms. As a non-empirical approach, it depends on secondary data from other academic research and industry reports, online materials, catalogues, indexes and databases found in libraries. It involves a systematic process of locating, evaluating and the combination of exiting information and scholarly work to address specific research question. The research design emphasises a qualitative combination of these sources to reveal patterns, themes and conceptual insight which enables or serves as a barrier to effective maternal health campaigns on social media platforms. Data for the study were collected through systemic review of literature published from sources including scholarly books, peer-reviewed journal articles and online materials. These materials provide diverse perspective on enablers and barriers to maternal health campaigns on social media platform

Discussion

This study discusses how social media serve as enablers and barriers to effective maternal health campaigns in Nigeria, by identifying areas like community engagements, digital literacy as enablers that can help the acceptance of maternal health campaigns on social media platforms, while misinformation and digital divide serve as barriers to the effectiveness of health campaigns on social media platforms. Okereke *et al* (2021) found in his study that during COVID-19 pandemic, women with low or no digital access experienced delay in receiving maternal health care. Olapegba *et al* (2021) noted that women in urban areas are more likely to benefit from social media health information than women in rural area.

Similarly, Abram & Axel (2024) investigated the rise of social media platforms in disseminating health information, but raised concern on the wide distribution of health misinformation and how it can influence health behaviour, shape public perspective and undermine trust in health authorities by exploring the consequence of health misinformation on social media platforms and exploring its impact on health outcome. The paper established that health misinformation can lead individuals to make poor health decision such as refusing lifesaving vaccines or avoiding necessary health decision. In another study, Massey & Srivastavi (2025) explored how social media are used by new parent in making decision, particularly in the context of misinformation. New parents face mounting health information dangers because they increasingly depend on social media as their information source.

Similarly, Jafar *et al* (2024) in his study observed that the growth of social media platform has both positive and negative impact on public health, noting that digital divide of unequal access and use of information and communication technologies. Pointing that digital inequality differs by gender, age and socioeconomic class within countries and suggest expanding digital access and reducing digital inequalities.

Social media serve as enablers and barriers of effective maternal health campaigns in Nigeria, by identifying areas like community engagements, digital literacy as enablers that can help the acceptance of maternal health campaigns on social media platforms, while misinformation and digital divide serve as barriers to the effectiveness of health campaigns on social media platforms. The barriers faced by maternal health campaign are seen to be effective by facilitating awareness on maternal health issues, promoting healthier maternal behaviour and extending reach of maternal information.

Conclusion

Social media have increased maternal health awareness in Nigeria and they are a double sword as they provide important health information and improve health outcomes by engaging community members, disseminating timely and useful information through its interactive features, but also allow the spread of misleading health information. To promote the effectiveness of maternal health campaigns on social media in Nigeria, the government and private sector should expand internet infrastructure, monitor and evaluate maternal health information online and carryout orientations on digital literacy and limit digital divide.

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